

SERIES OF REACTIONS IN NUCLEAR ASTROPHYSICS

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Compound nuclear reactions play an important role in many applications. Their cross sections are required input for astrophysical models that describe stellar evolution and nucleosynthesis and for modeling processes that are relevant to generating energy. Cross sections for neutron capture, neutron-induced fission, and other processes are required. Often the reactions of interest involve short-lived or highly radioactive target nuclei, which makes it difficult or impossible to measure their cross sections directly. To determine the cross sections of interest, indirect methods, such as inverse-kinematics experiments with radioactive beams, combined with theoretical treatments, are becoming increasingly important. This paper discusses recent progress of the surrogate nuclear reaction method, an indirect approach for determining cross sections for nuclear reactions $a + A \rightarrow B^* \rightarrow c + C$, that proceed through the formation of a compound nucleus (B^*). The method can be applied when the target is too short-lived to allow for a direct measurement, but a projectile-target combination can be found so that the compound nucleus of interest, B^* , can be produced in an alternative reaction $d + D \rightarrow B^* + b$. Cross sections for compound-nuclear reactions are required input for astrophysical models and nuclear-energy simulations.

An important goal of nuclear astrophysics research is to explain the origin of the heavy elements ($A > 56$). We have acquired a basic, but incomplete, understanding of the processes that generate the energy in stars such as our sun, that drive stellar evolution and that are responsible for the synthesis of the elements [1]. Nucleosynthesis of heavy elements beyond ^{56}Fe is known to take place primarily by neutron capture on lighter seed nuclei in the s (slow neutron-capture) and r (rapid neutron-capture) processes [2], with other processes contributing to the abundances of some specific isotopes. Models of these processes predict relative isotopic abundances for specific astrophysical scenarios. They require nuclear physics input and are constrained by measured isotopic abundances. The s process proceeds via neutron captures and beta decays through nuclides in and very near the valley of stability. Of particular interest to models of this process are neutron captures on s-process branch points, unstable nuclei with a life time long enough to allow the s process to proceed by either neutron capture or β decay. The strength with which one path dominates over the other depends on environmental variables, such as neutron density, temperature, and pressure, as well as on nuclear properties, specifically capture rates and beta-decay life times. Information on the astrophysical conditions can be inferred if the nuclear properties are known. Beyond being important for gaining a more detailed description of the s process

environments, reliable s-process abundances are crucial for our understanding of the r (rapid neutron-capture) process. The r process takes place in an environment with high temperature and high neutron flux. In such conditions the average time between neutron captures is much shorter than the life time for β -decay and reaction flows can proceed to very neutron-rich nuclei. Open questions include the exact path along the nuclear chart of the neutron captures and beta decays involved and the astrophysical site(s) of the process. Typically, r-process abundances are inferred by subtracting calculated s-process abundances from measured total abundances. This requires detailed calculations to predict s-process abundances, and reliable cross sections for neutron captures along the s-process path. Beta-decay half lives and nuclear masses, which determine nucleon separation energies, are considered to be the most important nuclear physics inputs for r-process models, as they determine the neutron capture path in scenarios that assume (n, γ) and (γ, n) reactions to be in equilibrium with each other, but models that do not invoke the equilibrium assumption require neutron capture rates for thousands of unstable nuclei. The world-wide growing demand for energy, coupled with increasing concern over pollution resulting from burning of fossil fuels, has resulted in renewed interest in nuclear energy. To exploit nuclear energy in a clean, efficient, and safe manner, concerns regarding reactor safety, waste handling, proliferation risks, and economic competitiveness have to be addressed. Advanced nuclear-energy systems may recycle actinides produced in conventional reactors or take advantage of alternative fuel cycles. A thorium-based fuel cycle, for instance, is appealing, since it produces less radiotoxic heavy transuranium isotopes than the conventional uranium-plutonium fuel cycle; thorium is also more abundant in the earth's crust than uranium. An important component of the research and development for these reactor concepts is the improvement of the fundamental nuclear data [4]. The transuranic nuclides, for example, play a much more prominent role in these new designs and yet the available cross-section data is quite limited. In addition, neutron-capture reactions could be used to incinerate long-lived fission fragments and therefore limit the challenges associated with the reactor waste. Sensitivity studies indicate that high-quality, reliable cross-section data are needed for neutron-induced reactions for a wide variety of radioactive isotopes covering neutron energies from thermal up to tens of MeV. In particular, capture and fission reactions on many of the isotopes of thorium, uranium, plutonium, and the minor actinides (such as ^{237}Np , $^{241}\text{--}^{243}\text{Am}$, and $^{244}\text{--}^{245}\text{Cm}$), as well as certain long-lived fission fragments. Many of these cross sections are extremely challenging to measure directly but significantly contribute to uncertainties in the reliable design and safe operation of a nuclear-energy system.

The appropriate formalism for the description of a compound-nuclear reaction $a + A \rightarrow B^* \rightarrow c + C$ is a statistical one. The objective of the surrogate method is to determine or constrain these decay probabilities experimentally.

Schematic representation of the “desired” (left) and “surrogate” (right) reaction mechanisms.

The basic idea of the surrogate approach is to replace the first step of the desired reaction, $a + A$, by an alternative (surrogate) reaction, $d + D \rightarrow b + B^*$, that populates the same compound nucleus. The subsequent decay of the compound nucleus into the relevant channel, $c + C$, can then be measured and used to extract the desired cross section.

Indirect approaches have to be developed in order to provide much-needed nuclear data, in particular cross sections for reactions on unstable isotopes. We have reviewed recent application of the surrogate nuclear reaction method, which aims at providing cross section information for compound nuclear reactions. Past applications of the surrogate method have demonstrated that it can provide useful cross section estimates for neutron-induced fission of actinides. Similar success in applications to neutron capture for a range of isotopes would be very valuable and remains to be demonstrated. Most analyses of the fission data carried out so far have made approximations that are likely to break down in situations relevant for extracting (n, γ) cross sections from surrogate measurements, making this a more challenging reaction to tackle. The examples discussed show this breakdown for capture reactions on Gadolinium isotopes. They underscore the need to take into account the different spin-parity distributions that occur in the desired and surrogate reactions.

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